

PROBLEMS OF THE MECHANICS OF WINDING THICK-WALLED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Division of the winding process into separate stages, consideration of compliance of semifabricated materials and introduction of circular models have allowed one to relate the process parameters and, above all, the winding tension with the properties of a finished article. Engineering methods for designing thick-walled elements, with technological history taken into account, and special-purpose structures have been developed. Novel technologies including those for fabricating spatially reinforced shaft lines the supporting structure of which is based on a system of a single thread, have been proposed and tested. The present research serves as a starting point for further studies and extension of works in the mechanics of winding undertaken in a number of scientific centers.

Keywords: mechanics of winding, models of winding process, thick-walled composite structure, composite flywheel, drive shaft.

1. INTRODUCTION

A winding operation is the basic fabrication technique for forming load-bearing structural elements made of polymer matrix-based fibrous composites, having the shape of bodies of revolution. Historically, developments in the winding technology may be traced back to 1370 B.C. There is the Ancient Egyptian flask [1] in the British Museum made, speaking in modern language, by winding the glass fibers from melt onto a dissolvable mandrel.

The semifabricated article to be wound possesses extremely low strength and stiffness in the radial direction. The creation of "a growing body" from such a material by layer-by-layer winding technique is associated with noticeable compressibility of circuits and redistribution of the preset tension N_0 .

The growth in article size is accompanied by the appearance and change of the system of initial stresses. This change continues in all the other stages of the winding process.

To calculate, analyse and control the diagrams of initial stresses, it is necessary to find the interrelation between the winding parameters, and first of all, tensioning and the properties of the finished product. It is possible to control tensioning only in the winding stage.

The technical theory of composite winding was evolved in the last years (see surveys [2,3]).

The problem of winding has not lost its actuality in nowadays. A series of Ph.D. Theses defended in Virginia State University, Stanford University, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, a series of work realised under J. Springer's leadership (see, e.g., [4]) and the works [5,6] have confirmed the above statement. In the survey the engineering their use in different areas of engineering were treated in consecutive order.

2. ENGINEERING MODELS

All through the technological history of winding process an essential change in physico-mechanical properties takes place. Besides, if the properties in the reinforcement direction remain linear and practically constant, the transverse compliance is essentially nonlinear and in the stages of winding, heat buildup and cure of the finished item can change by three orders. The application of a united rheological model to such a material is practically out of the question. The engineering methods consists in that on each stage the mechanical behavior is to be described by another rheological law.

A starting point in developing the engineering theory were the experiments using tensometric mandrels. It became possible to trace kinetics of pressure variation in all technological stages. The constancy of pressure on the mandrel in the process of polymerization is of special interest. This has allowed us to evolve various versions of the theory of initial stresses, neglecting the stage of polymerization. The dependency of initial stresses σ_{θ}^0 and σ_r^0 on the product geometry h/R , material anisotropy $\beta^2 = E_{\theta}/E_r$, the winding angle $\varphi(x, r)$, the number of circuits n , tension $N(h)$, and technological parameters of cure process $T(q, t, \tau)$ was established:

$$\sigma_{\theta}^0 \sim f(h/R, \beta, \varphi, N, n, T) \quad (1)$$

where q is contact pressure; t is temperature, and τ is cure time.

To analytically describe the variation of force in the process of winding, the circular models, based on a simplest piecewise-linear approximation of the nonlinear

Figure 1 Sequence of studying the models of winding stages: *a* - a linear circular model (1965), $\beta^2 \leq 1000$; *b* - a helically circular model (1971); *c* - approximation of the deformation characteristics of winding materials used for a nonlinear circular model (1973), $\beta_I, \beta_{II}, \beta_{III}$ - rigidity of the composite in the process of winding; *d* - a model of growing solid (1980), ω is a parameter of growth.

stress-strain diagram $\sigma_r - \epsilon_r$, were proposed. Their succession is shown in Figure 1. The concept is that the process of continuous force winding is substituted by the system of concentric rings, which are first mounted on the mandrel and then on each other under contact pressure equal to tensioning of the i -th layer. The widening of the range of thicknesses and operating pressures, when it is impossible to restrict oneself to one li-

near section of the stress-strain curve of material, asks for the models to be defined more precisely and the evaluation of the areas of their practical application.

Already the initial version of the model played an essential role in the development of technology of winding thick-walled structures. It was established that the total winding pressure on the mandrel P increases nonlinearly and approaches asymptotically a certain ultimate value:

$$P \approx \frac{n_0}{\kappa R_i} \arctan \sinh n\kappa \quad (2)$$

where $\kappa = \beta(c/R_i)$, R_i is the inner radius of the ring to be wound; c is the tape thickness. The critical number of circuits n_{cr} , beyond which the winding pressure on the mandrel does not increase any more, has been established:

$$n_{cr} = \frac{1}{\kappa} \ln \left(\frac{1}{\kappa} \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{\kappa^2}} \right) \quad (3)$$

Upon an incorrect selection of the force regime there appears a circular area over the product thickness where circuits pass into the compression area and this leads to instability in the form of irregular curvatures. Similar defects were most often found in thick-walled items. We succeeded not only in finding out the reasons for their appearance, but also proposed the ways of their elimination. The numerous experiments confirmed the conclusions made as a result of the analysis of circular models.

3. TECHNOLOGICAL MEANS

The nonlinearities of another nature should be taken into consideration in designing of cured items [2]. The development of design methods require that the peculiarities of composite behavior under loading across the reinforcement direction be considered and described. Especially this concerns the transverse tension strength σ_r^{tt} . Deep understanding of this characteristic is essential for the evaluation of the danger of cracking due to initial stresses, in the case of operating in the field of centrifugal forces and loading with concentrated forces.

The methods of designing rings and cylinders loaded by external pressure and with concentrated forces, with the physical nonlinearity if the relation $\sigma_r - \varepsilon_r$ taken into account, were evolved. In both cases the poor transverse tension strength and compressibility of a normal were the effects which have been neglected earlier. The consideration of the spiral placement of circuits has allowed us not only to find out and described the unique fracture mode in wound items - unwinding under pressure and in the field of centrifugal forces, but also to propose the methods for preventing this mode of fracture.

The technological procedures and processes have allowed us to design thick-walled wound structures without initial defects. The first one, by right, is the programmed winding. The gist is that tensioning is being varies according to a prescribed program to eliminate curvatures and compensate for thermoelastic tensile stresses having arisen in the cooling stage of the product together with the mandrel. This is the stage when crack formation and, consequently, also instability occur. In compliance with the properly selected program, it is possible to transmit the stress σ_r^{tt} into the zone of compression and avoid the danger of cracking and fiber curvatures. The experimental verification corroborated the high effectiveness of a programmed winding.

The range of variation of tensioning N_{max} is restricted from above by the strength of the semifabricated item, while the contact pressure $q = N_{max}/R$, besides that, also by the overall dimensions of the product to be wound, R . Therefore, novel methods are used to develop thick-walled wound structures: winding with layer-by-layer cure, introduction of compensating interlayers, and winding with extra pressure. These

methods in combination with the programmed winding have allowed us to design thick-walled products, the wall thickness of which is comparable to and sometimes equal to the inner radius.

One of the ways of reinforcing thick-walled products is the introduction of radial reinforcement. In such a way it is possible to greatly increase shear stiffness and transverse tension strength. The chord winding turned out to be effective for controlling the properties in the plane of winding; it is possible to control the anisotropy of properties by varying the angle of chord placement θ in the plane.

4. COMPOSITE FLYWHEELS

The experience accumulated in the mechanics of winding and design of thick-walled items, with their force and thermal history taken into account, is extremely useful for developing the analysis and design methods for composite flywheels, especially of their energy storing component - a thick-walled rim. The essential moment in the optimal design is obtaining of the structures with maximum energy storage capacity. This problem is bound up with minimization of integral terms in the expression for volume energy storage capacity:

$$W^v = W_{\max}^v - \left[\int_m^1 (\sigma_{\theta}^{\mu} - \sigma_{\theta}) r dr + \int_m^1 (\sigma_r^{\mu} - \sigma_r) r dr \right] \quad (4)$$

where m is the relative rim thickness.

The high specific strength of unidirectional composites in the direction of reinforcing fibers $\sigma_{\theta}^{\mu}/\rho$ (ρ is density) is the basic parameter indicative of the efficiency of flywheel material and it allow us to attain high mass energy storage capacity of rim flywheels made by circumferential winding technique. However this is true only for thin rings.

With increasing thickness the problem becomes bidirectional, i.e., not only circumferential σ_{θ} , but also radial σ_r stresses, poor transverse tension strength σ_r^{μ} , particularly of carbon fiber reinforced plastics, should be considered. Carbon fiber reinforced plastics are becoming the basic material used in flywheels. The low transverse tension and interlaminar shear strengths of unidirectional composites restrict considerably the ultimate rim thickness to be attained. This is the reason why the above considered methods of increasing load-carrying capacity of thick-walled items are efficient in the design and fabrication of composite flywheels. To these we can still add the ways of increasing the volume energy storage capacity as a result of surface treatment of carbon fibers, in particular, by plasma. The increase in shear strength is needed in flywheels operating in special deceleration regime.

5. DRIVE SHAFTS

A separate problem is the development of thick-walled wound rods [7] loaded in torsion. A characteristic example is shaft lines. It is a well-known fact that the fibrous composites behave poorly when loaded in torsion. The ways of increasing load-carrying capacity involve the increase in shear strength of a monolayer and ensuring the optimal law of tangential stresses distribution τ_{LT} over the radius of a rod, so that the potential of each layer might be fully utilized.

We succeeded in increasing the strength of a monolayer by properly selecting the optimal angle in the plane of fiber layup and run of the winding N . Special attention was paid to the fracture mechanism of a monolayer. The variation of the fiber layup angle over the radius $\varphi(r)$ allows to obtain the optimal diagram of shear stresses. We

obtained shear strength in torsion $\tau_{LT} = 400$ MPa and reached the relative wall thickness of the drive shaft h equal to the inner radius R of the drive shaft, i.e. $h/R \approx 1.0$.

Thick-walled wound structures can also be fabricated through multidirectional interweaving by a system of one thread [8]. When loaded in torsion, the axial deformations both - tensile and compressive - occur depending on the sign of moment or weaving step. The main difficulties are impregnation and squeezing over the external surface for the purpose of increasing reinforcement coefficient. This promising technology can also be used for braiding over the external surface of unidirectional thick-walled elements for the purpose of eliminating the danger of delamination due to poor transverse tension strength.

It is also possible to increase torsion strength of thick-walled product by means of spatial arrangement of straight fiber along the generatrices of hyperboloids of one sheet, whose centers are shifted along the longitudinal shaft axis for a specific step. According to the way of spatial bonds formation, this reinforcement pattern can be classified as a spatial scheme of reinforcing in the system of "one thread". The slope of straight generatrices of a one-sheet hyperboloid can be governed by the twist angle of thread systems, which were originally parallel to the generatrix. It is clear that the spatial arrangement of fibers leads not only to the increase in transverse tension and interlaminar shear strengths, but also to localization of fracture within several spatial cells. However torsional stiffness around the shaft axis decreases with increasing slope of the generatrix. The main difficulties in realizing this concept are technologic ones; a special equipment must be designed.

6. CONCLUSION

The division of the winding process into separate stages, consideration of interlaminar compliance of composites, and introduction of a circular model have allowed us to interrelate the parameters of the process and, above all, the winding tension with the properties of the finished article. The engineering methods for designing thick-walled wound elements and special-purpose structures have been developed with allowance for technological history. New technologies - proposed and realized, including processes for fabricating of spatially reinforced drive shafts, whose supporting framework is wound in the system of "one thread". The present research serves as the starting point for further developments and extension of works in the mechanics of winding undertaken in a number of leading scientific centers. The survey was originally published in Russian in full form in [9].

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